

The Universe with its Systems is Stable

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Why is the universe with its systems stable?

Let us consider the following diagram (Figure 1) as the universe with its systems. In this diagram, each circle denotes a star system like solar system. These systems in the universe are bound by gravitational attraction. The distance between any two consecutive systems in the universe remains unchanged in any direction; otherwise, the systems can collide with each other over the period of time. Therefore, the distances between systems of the universe are not possible to change. As a result, the universe with its systems is stable [1].

Figure 1. The Universe with its Systems.

Note that asteroids including any objects/particles other than planets in planetary system colliding with planets should not be taken into account.

References

- [1] Annamalai, C. (2025) The Universe with its Systems is Stable. Zenodo Preprints. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14864227>.